

STRATEGY FOR ACHIEVING GENDER EQUALITY.**Fayzieva Gulzoda Ulugbekovna**

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Research objective : Gender equality is a noble value that is important not only for ensuring human rights, but also for the political, socio-economic development of society. In addition, gender equality is one of the indicators showing the level of democratic development of the country. Therefore, in today's era of globalization, priority attention is paid to this issue in society.

Our interview with Nodira SHOTURSUNOVA, a member of the working group of the Commission on Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the chief adviser of the Secretariat of the Committee on Women and Gender Equality of the Oliy Majlis Senate, is about the work being done in this direction in our country and the future. it was about tasks.

Gender is an important social aspect of relations between men and women in all spheres of society's life and activity, including politics, economy, law, ideology and culture, education and science. In this respect, the concept of gender does not only represent the interests of women, but it also means that representatives of both sexes should be given the same opportunity to boldly move towards their dreams and goals, to improve the quality of life. One of the requirements of a developed society is to ensure the equal rights of men and women. After all, this balance in society is the guarantee of sustainable development and prosperous future of humanity. Therefore, this value has been highly respected in the history of human society since time immemorial.

If we pay attention to the legal development of gender equality, in this regard, it is permissible to recognize the universal principles defined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1948. It specifically recognizes the equality of men and women, and Article 1 of the Declaration states: "All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are given intelligence and conscience, so they should treat each other in a spirit of brotherhood. Another international document adopted by the UN in 1966 - the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, Article 3 states that "States participating in this Covenant shall enjoy all the civil and political rights set forth in this Covenant equally for men and women." undertakes to ensure its use", it was noted.

Our independent country, which has ratified these international documents, attaches serious importance to the issue of equality of women and men in its

national legislation based on the generally recognized requirements of international law. In particular, legal and practical work in this field has reached a new level in recent years. During the last four years, two laws, 6 decrees and decisions of the President, and 16 decisions of the government were adopted to ensure gender equality, support women, and increase their role in state and community management.

In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" adopted on September 2, 2019 is a comprehensive and basic legal document aimed at ensuring gender equality in our country. With this law, the concept of "gender" was defined for the first time in our national legislation. The law defined the main directions of state policy in the field of equal rights and opportunities for women and men, as well as state management mechanisms in this field. In particular, in order to prevent gender discrimination of women, a commission on ensuring gender equality was established in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It should be said that in recent years, special attention has been paid to ensuring equal rights of women and men, increasing the role of women in state administration, and appointing women to various responsible positions. As a result, our women work in responsible positions such as deputies, senators, governors, ambassadors, prosecutors, judges, and tax collectors.

In order to further increase the participation of women in state administration, a personnel reserve of more than 6,000 active women was formed. Currently, systematic training is being organized to prepare them for various leadership positions.

It should be said that although there are cases of violence against women in our lives, which has a negative impact on the development of the family and society, until recently this problem has been a closed topic. It was difficult to open a word about it.

In the last four years, the situation in this regard has changed radically, problems have been openly analyzed and their solutions have been sought. In particular, on September 2, 2019, on the initiative of the President, the adoption of the law "On the protection of women from oppression and violence" was an important step towards solving these problems. Currently, there are about two hundred centers for the rehabilitation and adaptation to life of victims of violence in our country. The association of non-governmental non-profit organizations established under the commission on issues of ensuring gender equality is also contributing to the work in this regard. In the conditions of the

coronavirus pandemic, the issue of protecting the rights of women and preventing harassment and violence against them is even more important. became a priority. In the implementation of the measures in this regard, hotlines were established in the system of the commission on ensuring gender equality. In addition, a special channel called "No Way to Violence" has been opened on the Telegram network. At the moment, these works are being continued consistently, and a special mobile application is being developed to provide legal and psychological assistance to women who have been subjected to violence, and to prevent cases of violence.

The work being carried out to support women in need of social protection is also having an important effect. Consistent work is being done to ensure women's employment and develop women's entrepreneurship. At the moment, the Gender Equality Commission is operating business advisory councils for the development of women's entrepreneurship. A forum of women entrepreneurs was established under the commission.